

MAPWORMS

Mimicking Adaptation
and Plasticity in
WORMS

D1.5 ANNUAL REPORT ON KEY COMMUNICATION EVENTS

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1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable gives an overview of the key communication activities of the MAPWORMS Consortium carried out in the first 12 months of the project. Dissemination and Communication (D&C) activities are crucial to the project overall success and serve as the driving force to maximise the impact of the project. These activities have been important from the project start in order to reach the widest possible audience and facilitate the use and take-up of results.

D&C activities are under continuous monitoring of the *WP1 - Project coordination, dissemination and communication* Leader - SSSA. All project partners are involved in D&C activities in order to foster awareness and transfer project results to general public and scientific, technical, and industrial communities. This ensures to cover all the research fields involved in the project (e.g. biology, soft robotics, chemistry, active soft actuators, DNA-hydrogels and mathematical modelling).

D&C activities are carried out according to *D1.4 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan*, which analyses the dissemination target audiences, the dissemination strategy approach, the project communication tools and dissemination events. The progress on D&C activities is reported in the present deliverable *D1.5 Annual report on key communication events*, and it will be updated in a new version at M30 with the deliverable *D1.8 Report on key communication events - 2nd reporting period*, and in the final version at M48 with the deliverable *D1.12 Reports on key communication event - 3rd reporting period* together with the deliverable *D1.16 Updated dissemination, communication and exploitation plan*.

1.1 MAPWORMS DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN

The MAPWORMS D&C activities aim at sharing research and pilot experiences throughout the EU and beyond. The Consortium believes particularly in the importance to foster research and entrepreneurship interest in new generations. Indeed, MAPWORMS aims to show to young people how science and engineering studies can positively impact the society at large.

Monthly online meetings of MAPWORMS Consortium are organized and serve also the purpose of continuous planning, supervision and improvement of D&C activities (11 monthly meetings were done in the first year of the project, Figure 1).

Figure 1. Print screen of one of the online monthly meetings.

In this framework, the current deliverable analyses the D&C activities of the Consortium carried out during the first year of the project. It gives an analytic presentation of the performance of our digital channels, our participation in physical and online events, our publications, etc.

2. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION CHANNELS

Specific D&C channels were set up at the beginning of the project, all of them based on the use of different digital tools. Nowadays, digital tools are the backbone of communication between an initiative and its target audience. MAPWORMS has devoted significant efforts towards its digital tools, especially website and social media, not only for exposing its outcomes to the target groups, but also for creating a community around the project with high interest in the developed innovative technology.

To this aim, SSSA has recruited a dedicated human resource with background in SEO Copywriting and Social Media Management. Her duty was playing the role of community manager and, by that meaning, she was in charge to create the conditions for the communication to work on both digital channels, website and social media. The objective of communication was to increase the level of engagement of the users organically (without any investment for advertising).

2.1 PROJECT WEBSITE

One of the main MAPWORMS D&C channels is the project website: www.mapworms.eu. It was developed by SSSA with the help of the entire Consortium at the beginning of the project and it is online since July 2022. The website is hosted and maintained by the Project Coordinator - SSSA, and it is the main front-end for reaching the different target groups and the main hub for communication activities. Indeed, the website provides information on project objectives, achievements, progress, results, and scientific outcomes; users can access multimedia and other dissemination contents by the website. Thus, the MAPWORMS project allows for sharing information about project results, public presentations and upcoming dissemination events. In terms of data sharing, we are following the FAIR Data Principles.

The style of the website was designed according to the MAPWORMS aims to show how science and engineering studies can positively impact the society at large. More details regarding the website design and structure can be found in *D1.1 Website and Project LOGO*. In the last months, in order to promote the website accessibility for everyone, a new plug-in is being evaluated to make both the MAPWORMS website and digital content accessible for the benefit of people with disabilities. An updated version of the website will be released in the next months as soon as the plug-in will be safely included in the current structure and properly debugged. The project website was created in the "mapworms.eu" domain. Considering future exploitation of results and sustainability of the project, the following additional domains have been also acquired:

- i. *mapworms.com*;
- ii. *mapworms.it*.

These domains are redirected in the principal **mapworms.eu**.

The website was also implemented with a SEO strategy in order to bring organic traffic to the website. SEO stands for **search engine optimization** and it is known as a digital technique used to naturally improve the organic traffic driven on a website, on a landing page, on an e-commerce, or also on social media.

Basically, SEO creates an invisible structure for human eyes, that helps Google's bots analysing each part of each page of the website and having a better orientation through all the information that it may contain. This is crucial for Google (and the other search engines in general) to value the authority of a website and to decide the position it should take on the SERP, i.e. the page where all the results of a research on the website are displayed.

With MAPWORMS, the main aim of implementing the SEO on the website is to drive more users naturally to find it while navigating the internet and using the targeted keywords, such as "robots", "robotics", "biorobotics", "smart materials", "smart technologies", "marine Annelida", "shape morphing robots" and whatsoever.

Analytics data of the project website are monitored and reported through the WP Statistics – WordPress plug-in that is implemented since July 2022. A summary of information about access to the MAPWORMS site obtained from WP Statistics – WordPress tool is reported below.

NUMBER OF VISITS AND VISITORS

The number of website visitors in the first 12 months was **1512**. The biggest number of users was in January 2022, which coincided with the 9th month of the project. There was a total number of **4548** visits occurred in the 12 months of the project. An illustration of both the number of visitors accessing the website and the number of visits is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. MAPWORMS website visitors and visits (July 2022 to April 2023) (Source: WP Statistics – WordPress).

The visitors of the MAPWORMS website come from several different countries. Most users are from the United States, Italy and United Kingdom. The distribution of visitors for the top 15 countries is shown in Figure 3.

Rank	Flag	Country	Visitor Count
1		United States	438
2		Italy	267
3		United Kingdom	87
4		India	74
5		Germany	65
6		Greece	52
7		France	46
8		Canada	44
9		Austria	40
10		Netherlands	29
11		Australia	28
12		Finland	26
13		Russian Federation	23
14		China	22
15		Singapore	21

Figure 3. Visitors' Demographics distribution (July 2022 to April 2023) (Source: WP Statistics – WordPress).

PAGE VIEWS

The 3 most visited pages of the website during the first 12 months of the project were “Contact”, “Project”, and “SSSA”; the top 10 pages are shown in Figure 4.

▲ Top Pages

ID	Title	Link	Visits
1	Contact	/contact/	761
2	Project	/project-1/	406
3	SSSA	/sssa/	223
4	Private Area	/private-area/	197
5	Results	/results/	196
6	HCMR	/hcmr/	174
7	Consortium Overview	/consortium-overview/	174
8	CONISMA	/conisma/	162
9	Vexlum	/vexlum/	156
10	information data protection	/information-data-protection	154

Figure 4. MAPWORMS page views (July 2022 to April 2023) (Source: WP Statistics – WordPress).

2.2 SOCIAL MEDIA NETWORKS

MAPWORMS profiles on popular communication channels and Social Networks, i.e., **Twitter®** (<https://twitter.com/mapworms>), **Facebook®** (<https://www.facebook.com/mapworms>), and **LinkedIn** (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/mapworms/>), were created during the first months of the project and constantly updated.

Behind the creation of each social media profile, there was an intense study on the social media platform and its potential related to the MAPWORMS project. It was immediately evident that not every channel was suitable to pursue the objectives we wanted to achieve with our communication strategies. Therefore, we chose LinkedIn, Facebook and Twitter to start with, where it could be found an active scientific community interested in the same subjects touched with MAPWORMS. In particular, this meant that there was a chance to:

- i. solicit a targeted audience's interest;
- ii. start a conversation that could reach a non-scientific audience;
- iii. bring more people closer to MAPWORMS and to the scientific field.

With these aims, it was chosen to adopt a friendly language to send the message in a simpler and more effective way.

Responsibility for social media channels is executed by the *WP1 - Project coordination, dissemination and communication* Leader, SSSA. Partners use both personal and organisation accounts (LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook) to disseminate contributions. A weekly contribution calendar was shared with the Consortium from the beginning of the project. By considering a constant rotation within the Partners, a new "post"/Twitter or notice was done for each project week. The Partners rotation assured variety in contributions and maintains the multidisciplinary approach of the project also in the social channels.

Access to the project social media channels is monitored and reported upon using the tools provided by each channel.

LINKEDIN

Figure 5 shows the distribution of LinkedIn clicks through the first 12 months of the project, and Figure 6 the engagement as organic impressions.

Figure 5. LinkedIn Post Clicks vs Time (May 2022 – April 2023).

Figure 6. LinkedIn Post Impressions for organic content vs Time (May 2022 – April 2023)

On the LinkedIn project account, there are 342 followers. Information is posted 1 times per week on average and the total amount of posts is 34. The top 2 posts on the MAPWORMS LinkedIn page obtained 2802 and 2055 impressions, respectively. The most popular post was about MAPWORMS kick-off meeting that happened on May 13th. 2022. The second most popular post was about the 3D printer located in Austria at the ACMIT GMBH centre.

Figure 7 shows the number of post reactions by followers on LinkedIn.

Figure 7. LinkedIn number of post reactions by followers (May 2022 – April 2023).

Table 1 contains values for metrics relating to the MAPWORMS LinkedIn page.

Table 1. Analysis of metrics of MAPWORMS LinkedIn page.

Metrics	Number
Total number of followers	342
Total number of original posts	34
Impressions	20820
Clicks	1392
Likes	463

TWITTER

The number of Followers on the MAPWORMS Twitter account is 12. Of the 23 Tweets created from the MAPWORMS account, there were 118 Likes. Table 2 contains values for metrics relating to the MAPWORMS Twitter account.

Table 2. Analysis of metrics of tweet activity.

Metrics	Number
Total number of original tweets	23
Impressions	3,700K
Engagements	4,67%
Likes	118

Information is posted on Twitter about 1 times a week on average. During the first 12 months of the project there were 23 posts tweeted. The top project tweet was posted in September 2022. It was about X-Ray images of a polychaete and got 994 impressions.

FACEBOOK

The number of Likes to the MAPWORMS Facebook page is 165 and the number of followers is 185. For the 32 Posts from the MAPWORMS account, there were 286 Likes. Table 3 contains values for metrics relating to the MAPWORMS Facebook account.

Table 3. Analysis of metrics of Facebook activity.

Metrics	Number
Total number of posts	32
Impressions	14,547K
Engagement	7,893K
Likes	286

Information is posted on Facebook 1 time a week on average. During the first 12 months of the project there were 27 posts. The top project post was posted in June 2022. It was about MAPWORMS kick-off meeting and got 39 reactions, 1 comment, and 6 reposts.

3. DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATIONS ACTIVITIES

This section reports on dissemination and communication activities, carried out during the first 12 months of the project.

3.1 PUBLICATIONS

The publications released by the MAPWORMS Consortium during the first year of the project are reported in Table 4.

It is worth to mention that all the project beneficiaries are putting in place actions to better comply with the Open Science Practice. "Gold" open access publishing is targeted whenever possible to favour large diffusion of MAPWORMS findings within the international scientific community. In the case the gold open access is not available (e.g. conference proceedings or abstract), the green open access will be adopted where authors make pre-prints available to the wider community. All the published contributions will be also archived in institutional or public repositories exploiting the very good means of the entire Consortium.

Table 4. MAPWORMS Publications M1-M12.

Author	Title	Journal/ conference	Type	Status	Date	DOI/ Link	Open Access	Comments
SSSA	A Bioinspired Fluid-Filled Soft Linear Actuator	Soft Robotics Journal	Journal	Published	Nov. 2022	DOI	Yes	
SSSA	Mimicking Adaptation and Plasticity in WORMS: the MAPWORMS Project	European Robotics Forum (ERF 2023)	Poster	Presented	Mar. 2023		No	The poster was presented during the ERF Forum but not published
SSSA	Mechanics of tubular meshes made of helical fibers and application to modeling McKibben artificial muscles	6th IEEE-RAS International Conference on Soft Robotics (RoboSoft 2023)	Poster	Presented	Apr. 2023		No	It will be published in IEEE Xplore in the next months.
CoNISMa	Marine annelids as models for innovative robots	81 st Congress of the Italian Zoological Union (UZI)	Poster	Presented	Sep. 2022		No	The poster was presented during the Forum but not published
HCMR	Scientific community needs: FAIR and credible data repositories. The case of MedOBIS Repository and MAPWORMS Project	International Ocean Data Conference - II (IODC-II)	Poster	Published	Mar. 2023	Link	Yes	The conference entitled "The data we need for the Ocean we want" took place at the UNESCO Headquarters in Paris
HUJI	Stimuli-Responsive DNA-Based Hydrogels On Surfaces for Switchable Bioelectrocatalysis and Controlled Release of Loads	ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces	Journal	Planned to send for publication	May 2023		Yes	
HUJI	Stiffness-Switchable Biocatalytic pH-Responsive DNA-Functionalized Polyacrylamide Cryogels and Their Mechanical Applications	Advanced Functional Materials	Journal	Planned to send for publication	June 2023		Yes	

3.2 PRESS RELEASES

The press releases carried out by the MAPWORMS Consortium during the first year of the project are reported in Table 5.

Table 5. MAPWORMS Press Releases M1-M12.

Author	Title	Magazine	Type	Status	Date	DOI/Link	Open Access	Comments
SSSA	The interaction between biology and engineering develops new bio-inspired robotic solutions in the medical field and for marine monitoring. MAPWORMS, coordinated by the BioRobotics Institute, is the new project funded by European Commission	Sant'Anna Magazine	Press release	Published	May 2022	Link	Yes	
HCMR	MAPWORMS: Mimicking Adaptation and Plasticity in worms	Cretalive news	Press release	Published	Dec. 2022	Link	Yes	This press release is in Greek
SSSA	Una nuova generazione di robot si prende cura degli uomini (a new robot generation takes care of humans)	Class	Press release	Published	Feb. 2023	Link	No	This press release is in Italian

3.3 EVENTS

During the first year of the project, MAPWORMS partners participated in a variety of events in the field of soft robotics, robotics, biology, chemistry, smart materials, and mathematical modelling, in order to increase the project visibility and reach further audiences with a wide range of backgrounds (Table 5). Active dissemination of the research results has been pursued at several high-level scientific worldwide conferences, covering the disciplines involved in the project. MAPWORMS partners participate in periodical open-days as well as to high-impact divulgation opportunities showcasing the project results and bringing researchers closer to the public. Furthermore, the research concept and its results have been presented to high-school students to attract their interest to science and research topics at the edge of science.

Informative material such as leaflets, internal reports, newsletters, fact sheets, user guides, etc. support and enhance the project dissemination. MAPWORMS leaflets – designed and defined from the first months of the project – were distributed by the Partners during all the conferences mentioned in the table and during any visit, workshop and talk. In addition, based on the structure of the scheduled events, posters were used as a valid dissemination mean for presenting the projects objectives, Consortium structures and obtained results.

Table 6. MAPWORMS events M1-M12.

Name	Date	Location	Type	Status	Partner	Contribution (organize/ participate)	Size audience	Web site	Comments
Scuola di Orientamento Universitario – 2022 at SSSA	23 June 2022	Pisa (Italy)	Presentation	Presentation for young students	SSSA		>50	Link	
Festival del pensare	24 July 2022	Montescudaio, Italy	Festival	Participated as invited speaker	SSSA	Workshop "Il mio amico robot"	>200	Link	Festival for general public
European Robotics Forum (ERF 2023)	14 – 16 March 2023	Odense, Denmark	Forum	Participated with poster	SSSA	Poster "Mimicking Adaptation and Plasticity in WORMS: the MAPWORMS Project"	>1000		
6th IEEE-RAS International	3-7 April 2023	Singapore	Conference	Participated	SSSA	Participated with poster entitled "Mechanics of	>2000	Link	

Conference on Soft Robotics (RoboSoft 2023)						tubular meshes made of helical fibers and application to modeling McKibben artificial muscles"			
International Ocean Data Conference - II (IODC-II)	20-21 March 2023	Paris, France	Conference	Participated	HCMR	Participate though the poster entitled "Scientific community needs: FAIR and credible data repositories. The case of MedOBIS Repository and MAPWORMS Project"	>300	Link	International Ocean Data Conference - II (IODC-II)
81 st Congress of the Italian Zoological Union (UZI)	20-23 September 2022	Trieste, Italy	Conference	Participated	CoNISMa	Participated with the poster "Marine annelids as models for innovative robots"	>200	Link	
Prof alla Torre!	04 August 2022	Porto Cesareo, Italy	Festival	Participated	CoNISMa	Presentation of the MAPWORMS project through the conference "Vermi marini robot"	>50		"Prof. alla Torre!" is the annual dissemination festival organised by the Marine Biology Museum of the University of Salento, aimed at introducing the marine biological research carried out at the University of Salento to the general public.
DNA-Nanotechnology	25-27 May 2022	Germany	Conf	Participated	HUJI	Invited speaker: Stimuli-Responsive DNA-based hydrogels And Their Applications	80		
MINERVA Center for Biohybrid Materials School	6-11 November 2022	Israel	MINERVA School conference	Participated	HUJI	Invited speaker: Stimuli-Responsive Hydrogels for Nanomedicine, Self-Healing and Mechanical Applications	90		
G-quadruplex Webinar	19 January 2023	Virtual	Webinar	Participated	HUJI	Invited speaker: G-Quadruplex Responsive Hydrogels and Interphases, and Their Applications	200		
2023 IEEE International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)	29 May – 2 June 2023	London (UK)	Conf	Planned	SSSA	Invited speaker at "Soft Robotics: Fusing function with structure" workshop	>500	Link	
Living Machines 2023	10-13 July 2023	Genoa (Italy)	Conf	Planned	SSSA	Organizer of "worm-inspired machines" workshop	>1000	Link	The workshop proposal was accepted
Prof alla Torre!	01 July – 10 August 2023	Porto Cesareo	Festival	Planned	CoNISMa	Presentation of the results of the first year of the MAPWORMS project	>50		

4. VIRTUAL GALLERIES OF THE VOUCHER SPECIMENS COLLECTION

Micro-CT scans of several annelid species have been started which will create an open virtual collection (Voucher Specimens Collection) uploaded in the MicroCTvlab online repository (MicroCTvlab @ <https://microct.portal.lifewatchgreece.eu/>) for any potential user (including academics, scientists, students, artists and animators and everyone who is interested in microCT data).

The MicroCTvlab will host annotated data and 3D models of the scanned annelids. This Voucher Specimens Collection will be uploaded in a web-based virtual lab (Micro-CTvlab) and a mobile application which will present virtual galleries of 3D micro-CT datasets of the annelid specimens and online tools for their manipulation and exploration (details will be reported in D1.10).

Figure 8 shows the microCTvlab web interface. Details about the functionalities of this virtual lab can be found in Keklikoglou et al. (2016)¹

Figure 8. The micro-CTvlab interface

¹ Keklikoglou K, Faulwetter S, Chatzinikolaou E, Michalakis N, Filiopoulou I, Minadakis N, Panteri E, Perantinos G, Gougousis A, Arvanitidis C (2016) Micro-CT : A web based virtual gallery of biological specimens using X-ray microtomography (micro-CT). Biodiversity Data Journal 4: e8740. <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.4.e8740>

5. MUSEUM EXHIBITIONS

Annelida specimens collected in the framework of MAPWORMS will be permanently exposed in the Museum of Marine Biology of the University of Salento (ca. 10.000-13.000 visitors/year + on line tours available) and multimedia panels will be used to describe annelid evolution, biology, ecology and to explain their potential as models for robotic applications profiting from MAPWORMS's results. Dissemination material with the MAPWORMS results can be also exposed in the [CretAquarium](#) which is located in Crete Island (Greece).

6. CONCLUSIONS

According to MAPWORMS GA, the main objective of this deliverable is to present the activities undertaken to transfer project results to the widest audience (both general public and scientific/technical/industrial communities) for the first reporting period M1-M12. Therefore, the document provides a report on digital communication tools, publications, events, other dissemination activities carried out during the first year of the project.

The actions carried out by the partners are diversified, ranging from publications, participation to conference and related events, publishing project information on MAPWORMS website, placing special effort in disseminating the project outreach via social media channels. The implementation of the Dissemination and Communication Plan is continuously monitored and assessed through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

As defined in the MAPWORM GA, a workshop on the project topics has been organized at the Living Machine conference (scheduled for July 2023). Two high-level papers per year had been defined as the main objective in terms of scientific publications. A paper was already published in the *Soft Robotics* journal (IF: 7.784), and other two papers are in preparation to be submitted to *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces* (IF: 10.383) and *Advanced Functional Materials* (IF: 19.924) journals in May and June 2023, respectively.

D&C activities on MAPWORMS overall vision and objectives want to reach a significant audience of people worldwide, thus targeting an estimated potential audience size > 10 000 000. As shown in Figure 3, the spatial distribution of the website visitors features a great variety of countries with users coming from United States, Italy, United Kingdom, and India at the top. However, a total number of 1512 website visitors was achieved during the first year (instead of the 15000 target value). Thus, more efforts will be spent on enhancing the accessibility of the project website and promoting it.

Among available social media, LinkedIn, Facebook, and Twitter have been chosen as the best channels for disseminating project results. LinkedIn turned out the most effective social media, and the account features 342 followers. This is probably due to the presence of a more scientific and technical audience's interest. Facebook was mainly used to reach the general public, and the MAPWORMS Facebook page obtained 185 followers. On the contrary, followers on Twitter (equal to 12) are still far from the target value of 100. Based on these results, in the future, we will focus on LinkedIn and Facebook to share new content and we will try to improve the project impact on Twitter.

This deliverable is a living document and the progress on D&C activities will be reported in the updated versions, namely *D1.8 Report on key communication events - 2nd reporting period* due at month M30, and *D1.12 Reports on key communication event - 3rd reporting period* due at month M48, together with the deliverable *D1.16 Updated dissemination, communication and exploitation plan* due at month M48.